

Human Trafficking in India

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ABSTRACT

Human trafficking is the third largest organised crime after drugs and arms trade across the globe. 80% of Human Trafficking across the globe is for sexual exploitation. Human trafficking is one of the major problems in India. In 2016 about 23000 of human trafficking case is reported in India and the no. is increasing in each passing year. West Bengal ranked highest in Human trafficking cases. Around 40% of human trafficking is from West Bengal followed by Assam, Rajasthan, and Gujarat etc. The reasons for human trafficking are lack of education, poverty, political instability, corruption, poor legal system etc. Reasons of human trafficking are Forced marriage, bonded labour, sexual exploitation, organ trade racket etc. Statistical data on human trafficking in India and suggesting how it can be controlled.

Keywords: *Meaning-Problems-Reasons-Statistical data - Suggestion*

INTRODUCTION

Human Trafficking means trade of human being for exploitative purposes including bonded and forced labour, commercial sexual exploitation and illegal organ-trade. Article 3, paragraph (a) of the Protocol to Prevent, Suppress and Punish Trafficking in Persons defines Trafficking in Persons as the recruitment, transportation, transfer, harbouring or receipt of persons, by means of the threat or use of force or other forms of coercion, of abduction, of fraud, of deception, of the abuse of power or of a position of vulnerability or of the giving or receiving of payments or benefits to achieve the consent of a person having control over another person, for the purpose of exploitation. It is the third largest

organised crime after drugs and arms trade across the globe. 80% of human trafficking across the globe is for sexual exploitation. Human Trafficking is one of the major problem in India. India is considered the hub of the crime in Asia.

Why Human trafficking is high in India ?

Human Trafficking is high mainly for the migration of men for work to commercial cities and from here the demand for commercial sex is created. Woman and girl child who are born in the poor family is mainly the victims of Human Trafficking. The girl child born in a poor family of the north eastern part of India is at high risk as their parents are desperate to sell their daughter to earn money and get rid of them. Poor families think that a girl child is a sin to the family as they are consider incapable to earn enough money for their family and at the same time during marriage of a girl child the parents have to give dowry to her in laws.

Other causes for human trafficking in India are as follows:

Lack of education: Most Indian villages do not have schools. The schools that exist are in very poor condition. Teachers are not well trained in the villages because of the poor salaries offered, inadequate work environments, and transportation issues. Which leads most of the children have little to no education. This gives opportunities to traffickers to make fake promises to parents, luring them to send their girls away for a chance at better education, domestic work, and other “good” opportunities that would otherwise be unattainable in their lifetimes.

Caste system: India still believes in caste system. The lower castes, which contain the majority of the population, have less opportunity for advancement than those in the higher castes. The lower castes are vulnerable to all kinds of exploitation in Indian society. The upper castes intimidate, manipulate, and coerce lower caste girls for sexual pleasure.

Gender- related difference: In Indian culture, boys are more preferable over girls. This leads to abortion of girl child when sex comes to know... The use of ultrasounds to detect the baby's gender is extremely prevalent in India today. Women undergo ultrasounds to determine the sex of their unborn babies in order to decide whether or not to abort... As a result of the bias against females, there is a big inequality in the boy-girl ratio in India. For every 1000 boys, there are only 880 girls. Girls are sometimes trafficked as housemaids so that the boys in a house can have a common girl within the house. After a couple of years, she will be sold into the brothels, and the family gets another girl for the boys. This is a trend that occurs mainly in the northern part of India.

City Life Dream: The village people think that the city will improve their standard of living. When traffickers offer their daughters a job in the city, the villagers hope that soon their life is going to change.

Poor awareness of Human Trafficking and Brothel life: The village people are illiterate and they are unable to predict the intention of the trafficker which ends up landing into brothels and other places in major cities.

Corruption in India: Our political system is corrupted, thus contributing to poverty, human trafficking, democracy debasement, inequality in wealth distribution, social injustice, and the widespread giving and taking of bribes. According to a Transparency International (TI) report on global corruption, India has fallen to 74th place on the list of 180 nations evaluated. Widespread unemployment, the desire to make a quick profit with little effort, and the broad existence of gangs create an atmosphere conducive for trafficking in persons to thrive.

Political instability: In the last few years, political instability in the country has contributed to lawlessness and an inability of the government to contain the criminal activities that have resulted. In order to maintain stability, political parties have been forced to placate one another with favours and concessions which allow for extensive "cover ups"

that often go unnoticed within society. The police are often not independent entities in India. Instead, each state's force is managed by a political leader who controls their daily activities. As a result, the police are drawn into the corruption of the political system.

Lack of legal convictions against traffickers in India: The Indian court system is overcrowded due to an increasingly cases and delay in decision making... The increasing crime rate in Indian society has become a burden to current judicial system to handle. Corruption has also crept into the judicial system. The writs of petition that come to the high court of India will often take eight to ten years to be heard.

High market for Minor Demand: Worldwide there is a high demand for minor girls in the sex trade. India is no different. Minor girls are easy targets for exploitation. They are afraid to speak out about the crimes that are committed against them, and they typically remain very obedient to the customers. Foreign tourists prefer minor girls for both their youthful appearances and their submissiveness to them. Young girls are very desirable for both brothel owners and customers.

Why human is been trafficked?

The human trafficking is done for the following reasons are as followed:

Forced marriage: Other than prostitution girls are bought and sold in many part of the country as ratio of men is comparatively more than women due to female infanticide which lead to forced marriage.

Bonded Labour: Poor people running out of cash sell their kids to earn money. Both boys and girls are sold and are not paid for many years.

Sexual exploitation: Sexual exploitation is the sexual abuse of girl child and women through the exchange of sex or sexual acts for drugs, food, shelter, protection, other basics of life, and/or money. Sexual exploitation includes involving girl child and women in creating pornography and sexually explicit websites.

Organ Trade Racket: Traffickers show fake hopes to poor people of earning good amount of money for living a standard life but actually they sell their body parts and leave them in roads or sell them in brothel.

Statistical data of human trafficking in India

In the year 2016, more than 8000 cases of Human Trafficking had been lodged . While 23000, out of which 182 are Foreigner had been rescued during the year as per National Crime Record Bureau in India.

In previous year, out of 8132 cases were reported from crossed the country which is 1255 cases more than 2015. Out of 15379 victims, 58% of them are below 18 years of age according to NCRB statistic crime report in 2016.

Out of 29 states West Bengal ranked topped in human trafficking in 2016. 3579 Cases have been reported which is 18.5% more than 2015. Assam ranked second, in 2016 1.12% cases of human trafficking had been reported. Followed by Rajasthan 1422 cases, Gujarat 548 cases, Maharashtra 517 cases and Tamil Nadu 434 cases. Delhi ranked 14th in Human Trafficking.

A total of 23117 of victims of Human Trafficking are rescued in 2016.

Human trafficking, prohibited under Article 23 (1) of the Constitution, followed by forced labour, sexual exploitation or prostitution, domestic servitude, forced marriage, begging, adoption, child pornography and organ transplant.

How to stop Human Trafficking in India?

Thus we can stop human trafficking by reaching to more people and try to convince them that girl child is not a sin to family .Government should that necessary steps to educate people, irradiate poverty, stop corruption, caste biased decision, and gender related difference in India. We should take a step forward to inform poor people about Human Trafficking, what they do with their girl child and how to identify them. Therefore we the people of the India should work together to stop human trafficking and creating a healthy society for a girl child.

